

Analysis of Plane and Three Dimensional Trusses Subjected to Mechanical and Thermal Loadings.

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Abstract: A finite element program has been developed for analysis of plane and three dimensional trusses under mechanical and thermal loading. Trusses under combination of both the loading have also been analyzed. The finite element program has been written in Fortran language. A two node truss element has been used for analysis of trusses. The direct stiffness method has been adopted for generation of element stiffness matrix. The deflections at the nodes and forces developed in the member obtained by the present analysis have been compared with the published results. It is seen that there is a close agreement between the present solutions and the published results. Few practical examples related to three dimensional roof trusses and electrical towers have been presented.

Mathematical Formulation

A bar element is taken for the analysis. It is assumed that the members can elongate or contract only in axial direction. So obviously the element has one degree of freedom per node. So the element has two degree of freedom and obviously the size of the element stiffness matrix is 2x2. The element stiffness matrix $[k_{el}]$ in local axis coordinate system may be written as

$$[K_{el}] = \frac{AE}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \text{ Where } L, E \text{ and } A \text{ are length Young's modulus and cross sectional area of}$$

the member. As the orientation of the axis of the individual members of the truss is different, they must be expressed in a common axis system. So the stiffness matrix $[k_{el}]$ of all the members is transformed in global axis system. The element stiffness matrix $[k_{eg}]$ in global axis system is written as

$$[k_{eg}] = [T]^T [k_{el}] [T], \text{ where } [T] \text{ is the transformation matrix which may be expressed as,}$$

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} l & m & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & l & m \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{Where } l = \cos \theta, \quad m = \sin \theta \text{ and } \theta \text{ is the angle between axis of the}$$

element and the global x-axis as shown in Fig.1.

After determining the stiffness matrices of all the elements of the truss in the global coordinate system, they are assembled together in the proper order to get the overall stiffness $[K_0]$. After incorporating the boundary conditions, in the overall system of equations, it is solved to get the nodal displacements of the structure. The stress of the members can be solved with the help of nodal displacements.

When thermal loading effects are considered then only the load vector is to be changed but stiffness matrix will remain same. If T and α are the change of temperature of the whole structure and coefficient of thermal expansion of the truss members respectively, the thermal expansion is $T \alpha L$. So the strain and stress developed in the members are $T \alpha$ and $T \alpha E$. Then thermal load in the members is $T \alpha EA$.

Thermal load in the member in x-direction $T \alpha EA l$

Thermal load in the member in y-direction = $T \alpha EA m$

The temperature load in the member in global coordinate system = $EAT \alpha [-l \quad -m \quad l \quad l]^T$

The temperature load along with the other externally applied loads are assembled together to get the nodal load vector. For space truss the transformation matrix $[T]$ is given by

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} l & m & n & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & l & m & n \end{bmatrix}$$

Where l , m and n are the direction cosines of the local x' axis with respect to the global x , y and z axes respectively. The element temperature load for space truss in the global coordinate system as expressed as $EAT\alpha[-l \ -m \ -n \ l \ m \ n]^T$.

Example: A space truss as shown in Fig. is considered. Young modulus, cross-sectional area and coefficient of thermal expansion of the members are 200.0 Gpa, 900.0 mm² 1.0x10⁻⁶ per °C respectively. There increased an increase in temperature of 50⁰C of all the members. The structure is also subjected with an applied load of 5.0 kN as shown in Fig. 2 The deflection of the nodes and the member forces are presented in the Table 1 and Table 2.. Nodes 1, 2 and are hinged joint.

Table 1. Displacements of the nodes (u, v, w) along x, y, z directions under different loads..

Nodes	Only mechanical load			Only thermal load			Combination of both loads		
	u x 10 ⁻³	v x 10 ⁻³	w x 10 ⁻³	u x 10 ⁻³	v x 10 ⁻³	w x 10 ⁻³	u x 10 ⁻³	v x 10 ⁻³	w x 10 ⁻³
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
4	-0.1887	-0.1111	-0.0555	-0.0125	-0.0125	0.0250	-0.2011	-0.1236	0.0305
5	-0.1957	-0.4285	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0250	-0.1957	-0.4285	0.0250
6	0.1021	-0.1111	0.0555	-0.0250	0.0	0.0250	0.0770	-0.1111	0.0805
7	-0.4400	-0.3889	-0.0833	-0.0125	-0.0125	0.0500	-0.4545	-0.4014	-0.0333
8	-0.4469	-0.9681	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0500	-0.4469	-0.9681	-0.0500
9	0.1127	-0.3889	0.0833	-0.0250	0.0	0.0500	0.0876	-0.3889	0.1333

Fig. 2

Table 2. Member forces generated under mechanical, thermal and combine loads.

Member No.	Mechanical load	Thermal load	Combine loads
1-2	0.0	-8999.99 (C)	-8999.99 (C)
1-3	0.0	-8999.99 (C)	-8999.99 (C)
2-3	0.0	-8999.99 (C)	-8999.99 (C)
1-4	-19999.58 (C)	0.01	-19999.57
2-5	-0.21 (C) (C)	0.0	-0.21
3-6	20000.0	0.0	20000.0
2-4	11180.15	0.0	11180.15
3-4	-0.01 (C)	-0.01 (C)	-0.03
2-6	-12247.5 (C)	0.0	-12247.5
4-5	-4999.87 (C)	-0.03 (C)	-4999.87
4-6	0.0	0.0	0.0
5-6	7071.10	0.06	7071.10
4-7	-9999.76 (C)	0.01	-9999.76
5-8	0.0	0.0	0.0
6-9	10000.0	0.0	10000.0
5-7	11180.11	0.01 (T)	11180.11
6-7	-0.03 (C)	0.01 (T)	0.01
5-9	-12247.46 (C)	0.01 (T)	-12247.46
7-8	-4999.90 (C)	0.13 (T)	-4999.90
7-9	-0.06 (C)	0.15 (T)	-0.06
8-9	7071.03	0.03 (T)	7071.03

Fig. 2

Numerical Examples.

Example 1.

In this example a four bar truss (Fig.1) is considered. The young modulus, coefficient of thermal expansion and cross sectional area of the member are $E = 29.5 \times 10^6$ psi, $\alpha = 1/150000$ per $^{\circ}\text{F}$ and 1.0 sq. inch. There is an increase in temperature of 50°F in the bar 2 and 3 only. There is no other load on the structure. The nodal displacement and member forces are given in Table 1 and are compared with the values obtained from T. R. Chandrupatia and A. D. Belegundu [1]. The results obtained by the present analysis have close agreement with those of T. R. Chandrupatia and A. D. Belegundu [1].

Fig. 1

Table 1. Longitudinal displacement (u), transverse displacement (v) and member forces of the truss under thermal load.

Displacement u (in)			Displacement v (in)		Member forces		
Node No.	Present	Ref.	Present	Ref.	Member No.	Present	Ref.
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1-2	0.0	0.0
2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2-3	2185.18	2183
3	0.00391	0.00391	0.01222	0.01222	1-3	-3641.97	-3643
4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4-3	2913.57	2914

Example 2.

In this example the same truss as discussed in example 1 is considered. The analysis is performed under mechanical loading as well as combination of mechanical and thermal loading as shown in Fig. 1. In case of combined loading, temperature of the members 2 and 3 are increased by 50 °F. Results obtained are presented in Table 2 and Table 3 with those of T. R. Chandrupatia and A. D. Belegundu [1]. It is seen that present results obtained are very close to that of T. R. Chandrupatia and A. D. Belegundu [1].

Table 2. Comparison of longitudinal displacement (u), transverse displacement (v) and member forces of the truss under mechanical loading.

Displacement u (in)			Displacement v (in)		Member forces		
Node No.	Present	Ref.	Present	Ref.	Member No.	Present	Ref.
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1-2	20000.0	20000.0
2	0.02712	0.02712	0.0	0.0	2-3	-21875.0	-21880.0
3	0.00565	0.00565	-0.02225	0.02225	1-3	-5208.33	-5208.0
4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4-3	4166.66	4167.0

Table 3. Comparison of longitudinal displacement (u), transverse displacement (v) and member forces of the truss under combine mechanical and thermal loading.

Displacement u (in)		Displacement v (in)		Member forces	
Node No.	Present	Present		Member No.	Present
1	0.0	0.0		1-2	20000.0
2	0.02712	0.0		2-3	-19689.8
3	0.0096	-0.01		1-3	-8850.3
4	0.0	0.0		4-3	7080.2

Fig. 4

Example 3.

In this example a space truss as shown in Fig. 3 is considered. The cross-sectional areas of the members and the loads acting are given in Table 4 respectively. The analysis is performed under mechanical loading as well as combination of mechanical and thermal loadings. In case of combined loading, temperature of all the members are increased by 50 °F Young modulus and coefficient of thermal expansions of the members are taken as $E = 2.1 \times 10^4$ kN/cm² and $\alpha = 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$ per °C respectively.

Table 4

Member	Cross-sectional	Node no.	Load (kN)
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	area cm ²		X	Y	Z
9-10, 7-9, 8-10, 6-9, 5-10	10.47	5	-2.3		
7-10, 6-10, 8-9, 5-9, 5-8, 6-7, 7-8, 5-6, 1-8, 4-5, 2-7	19.03	8	-2.3		
3-6, 4-7, 3-8, 1-6	21.06	9	-4.5	-45.0	-23.0
1-5, 4-8, 2-6, 3-7	42.12	10		-45.0	-23.0

Table 5. Displacements (u, v and w) of the nodes and member forces of the truss under mechanical loading.

Node No.	Displace. u (cm)	Displace. v (cm)	Displace. w (cm)	Member	Member Force (kN)	
					Present	Ref.
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	9-10	1.69	
2	0.0	0.0	0.0	7-9	-23.66	
3	0.0	0.0	0.0	8-10	-19.77	
4	0.0	0.0	0.0	6-9	12.96	
5	-0.00021	-0.0022	-0.0233	5-10	16.85	
6	-0.0023	-0.0021	-0.0214	7-10	-59.51	
7	0.0008	-0.0023	-0.0346	6-10	37.30	
8	-0.0033	-0.0022	-0.0326	8-9	-56.35	
9	0.0096	0.1672	-0.0103	5-9	40.46	
10	0.0110	-0.1672	-0.01461	5-8	0.05	
				6-7	0.60	
				7-8	-9.86	
				5-6	4.87	
				1-8	-14.79	
				4-5	10.97	
				2-7	-16.58	
				3-6	9.18	
				4-7	-20.04	
				3-8	-20.84	
				1-6	13.93	

				2-5	13.13	
				1-5	49.70	49.70
				4-8	-63.97	-63.97
				2-6	42.56	42.56
				3-7	-71.11	-71.11

Reference

1. T. R. Chandrupatia and A. D. Belegundu, Introduction to finite elements in engineering, 3rd. edition, Prentice-Hall, 2002.
2. **Introduction.**
3. In finite element method, problems with irregular geometry and having different materials and also different types of loading can be tackled comfortably. One of the main reasons for the popularity of the method in different field of engineering is that once a general computer programming is written it can be used for solution of any problem of similar type simply by changing the data.